

The Future of Open Environmental Data Infrastructure

September 2025 | Workshop Report

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Executive Summary

Since January 2025, the nation has witnessed the systematic dismantling of foundational environmental data infrastructure. Yet amid this crisis, there are both bright spots and opportunities. In September 2025, OEDP and our partners convened a cross-sector network of researchers, community leaders, data stewards, technologists, civil society advocates, government stakeholders, and funders to chart a course toward resilient, just, and open environmental data systems. This report captures what emerged. Below are key insights, as well as six active sprint projects catalyzed at the convening.

The crisis is a systems crisis, not just a data crisis. Federal suppression of environmental information, massive personnel cuts, erosion of institutional capacity, and loss of public trust compound one another. Data preservation alone cannot solve these issues. The field needs new governance models, sustainable funding mechanisms, legal protections, coordination infrastructure, and cultural change around how communities participate in data systems.

Fragmentation creates both vulnerability and opportunity. Lack of coordination makes the field less effective and efficient, but the diversity of approaches—rapid archiving, tool restoration, policy advocacy, coalition building, human capacity investment, legal strategy—provides resilience. No single organization or strategy can address all dimensions of the challenge. The question is not whether to consolidate but how to best coordinate a federated data environment.

Community leadership must be structural, not aspirational. We are all affected by the destruction of federal data infrastructure, and environmental justice communities face disproportionate harms, both by the erasure of data and proliferating pollution sources (like data centers). Making data systems truly community-centered requires enforceable control over data collection, use, and interpretation. It requires data quality sufficient for legal challenges, integration of community-generated evidence, and recognition of lived experience as authoritative knowledge.

The federal government's role is irreplaceable and must be defended. Stop-gap measures and distributed capacity are essential now, but cannot substitute for federal investment in essential datasets that only the government can produce at scale (satellite systems, census data, nationwide environmental monitoring). The field must simultaneously step up where possible and advocate for and with federal partners to build more durable federal data capacity and protections.

Sustainable infrastructure requires sustainable funding. Volunteer heroics and short-term crisis funding have carried the field through initial shock, but burnout looms. Data stewardship must be properly resourced. New funding models that acknowledge the commercial value of public data while maintaining public access deserve attention.

Legal strategy must evolve. With courts having expanded power to evaluate agency science, establishing what constitutes reliable environmental data becomes critical. Environmental litigators need to be educated about data science and preservation, and data scientists need to understand evidentiary standards. The intersection of data quality, legal defensibility, and community control will shape whether data can drive accountability.

Emerging Sprints

Against this backdrop, members of the workshop identified six key themes that should be the focus of ongoing work on the future of open environmental data infrastructure. We've organized them into the following sprints:

- **Sprint 1: Building Capacity of Data Stewards**
Pilot and document key strategies to increase knowledge around data stewardship and build volunteer capacity, creating shareable best practices for improving volunteer retention and satisfaction.
- **Sprint 2: New Funding Models and Sustainable Infrastructure**
Federate organizations to generate diversified, sustainable funding for public environmental data infrastructure by exploring how commercial uses of publicly-funded data could generate revenue that flows back to research and infrastructure.
- **Sprint 3: Cross-Organizational Coordination**
Develop a coordinating body through a phased process starting with landscape analysis, bring groups together for briefing and participation, create a leadership task force, and pilot coordination around greenhouse gas emissions data as an immediate test case.
- **Sprint 4: Community-Generated and -Validated Data**
Conduct a discovery process to examine how to pair qualitative and quantitative data, define validation standards respecting multiple forms of evidence, identify projects doing this well, and compile examples with transparent tradeoffs into an implementation toolkit.
- **Sprint 5: Legal, Policy, and Legislative Strategies**
Form a working group to analyze legal protections and litigation issues and scope a rapid response strategy. Simultaneously work with data stewards to codify QA/QC procedures and develop validation systems that satisfy both scientific standards and legal requirements.
- **Sprint 6: Data Interoperability and Communities of Practice**
Build communities of practice around cross-domain interoperability standards (learning from models like CMIP, AgMIP, and genomics frameworks) and dataset-specific quality assessment. Create spaces to share knowledge about data quality issues and appropriate use cases.

Introduction: Why This, Why Now

Since January 2025, the nation has witnessed the systematic dismantling of foundational environmental data infrastructure: datasets removed or defunded, long-standing public tools taken offline, and access to climate and environmental health information quietly rolled back. Widespread federal layoffs, hiring freezes, and the shuttering of key agency offices have hollowed out the offices and programs that collect, curate, document, and operationalize environmental information.

The consequences extend far beyond government websites. This infrastructure collapse disproportionately harms environmental justice communities, who already face higher burdens in documenting and addressing environmental harms. Information asymmetries are widening as trusted public-interest tools disappear. The fragility of solely federally-hosted resources, long evident to those working in this space, has become undeniable.

Yet amid this crisis, there are bright spots. Grassroots archiving networks mobilized rapidly to preserve threatened data. New collaborations emerged across sectors. Private funders stepped up investments in science and data infrastructure. These efforts revealed both the strength of the environmental data community and the seeds of a more durable, equitable infrastructure.

This moment demands more than reactive preservation. It calls for collective visioning: What kind of infrastructure do we want to build? What technical, institutional, legal, and relational scaffolding can sustain it? How do we move from triage to long-term systems change?

In September 2025, the Open Environmental Data Project (OEDP), in partnership with the Public Environmental Data Partners coalition (PEDP), the Center for Open Data Enterprise (CODE), and the Kapor Foundation, convened a cross-sector network of researchers, community leaders, data stewards, technologists, civil society advocates, government stakeholders, and funders in Oakland, California. Over two days, this group gathered to chart a course toward resilient, just, and open environmental data systems.

This report captures what emerged from that convening: the survey of where environmental data infrastructure stands in 2025, the existing work we elevated and learned from, the gaps we identified in current coordination efforts, and critically, the priority areas for exploration, strategy, and action, including concrete sprints that participants committed to pursue.

The future we envision is not a return to the status quo of 2024. The previous state of U.S. environmental data infrastructure had significant shortcomings: data was siloed and out-of-date, poorly interoperable, often difficult to access and use, frequently inattentive to community needs, and rarely integrated across sources to reflect communities' lived experiences or to leverage higher quality or more granular data. Instead, we are working toward something better: an infrastructure that is community-centered, justice-oriented, supportive of timely application, federated but not centralized, and resilient by design. This report documents the beginning of that journey.

What Are We Up Against?

The workshop opened with a sobering assessment of the current landscape. Four presenters offered different lenses on the challenges facing environmental data infrastructure in 2025, revealing both the breadth and interconnection of the threats.

Climate of Suppression: The Scale and Targeting of Data Removal

Dr. Gretchen Gehrke of the Environmental Data & Governance Initiative (EDGI) presented findings from their report "Climate of Suppression: Environmental Information Under the Second Trump Administration." The data painted a stark picture: in EDGI's monitoring samples, there were 70% more significant changes to federal environmental websites in the first 100 days of the second Trump administration compared to the first term.

Furthermore, EDGI's analysis revealed clear targeting of three primary areas: environmental justice and equity, climate change, and scientific integrity. The changes take multiple forms—language alterations that shift meaning, deletion of critical context, and outright removal of webpages and tools. Particularly concerning is the removal of tools that enable public engagement with data, the stagnation of previously updated datasets, and the discontinuation of data collection programs.

This information suppression accompanies attacks on other pillars of environmental governance: the dismantling of rules and regulations (including NEPA implementation rules and greenhouse gas reporting), dramatic budget and staffing cuts (an estimated 25-33% reduction in EPA staff, USGS field technicians with zero travel budgets, shuttering of offices across agencies), and a broader agenda to reshape the federal government to create "epistemologies of ignorance." Critically, existing policies have proven insufficient to protect data and information from removal.

America's Data Future: Building Resilient Capacity

Joel Gurin of the Center for Open Data Enterprise (CODE) broadened the lens to consider not just what is being lost, but what infrastructure and capacity the field needs to build. Drawing on CODE's work with USAFacts and the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation's health data projects, Gurin outlined several priority areas:

- **Preserving core data and tools** remains an urgent, ongoing need. Monitoring projects must continue to track removals and alterations, although preservation alone is insufficient.
- **Non-federal capacity** must be assessed and strengthened to potentially backfill federal data gaps, raising the question of whether state, local, and community entities can realistically compensate for federal rollbacks. The field also needs to better understand what NGOs are collecting and how to integrate these sources appropriately while respecting their distinct governance and purposes.
- **Data privacy reform** has become urgent as public trust in government data collection erodes. Without trust in how their data will be used, people won't respond to surveys, creating a vicious cycle that undermines the data collection fundamental to evidence-based policy.
- **Messaging, communications, and advocacy** must evolve to better communicate the value of public data to broader audiences, building the constituency needed to defend it.
- **Legislative and policy protections** need to be developed that go beyond the Evidence Act to create more durable safeguards for data infrastructure, ensuring resources are protected regardless of which administration is in power.

The Ocean Data Crisis: People, Technology, Policy, and Purpose

Kate Wing of Intertidal Agency turned towards the physical infrastructure of data collection, focusing on ocean and earth observation systems where challenges span every dimension of the data lifecycle, and raising several lessons for data infrastructure writ large:

- **People are the foundation.** Humans must be involved throughout the data lifecycle. The federal layoffs represent both institutional capacity losses and the erosion of expertise that cannot be quickly rebuilt.
- **Technology infrastructure faces existential threats.** The US has historically funded the majority of global ocean observations, from satellites to monitoring sensors and the ships that deploy them. These observations provide fundamental data like ocean temperature and sea level to models for weather forecasts, shipping routes, and local disaster planning, among many other uses. The power of these observations comes from their continuity and comprehensive coverage. Recent policy shifts to privatize ocean infrastructure jeopardize this coverage, concentrate risk, and reduce public control.
- **Policy and process distinctions matter.** Wing drew an important line between earth observation data and compliance documentation. While compliance documents have historically not been public, they may become increasingly important as federal observation systems falter. Repository policies that require researchers to publish in open repositories provide one form of resilience, but only if they remain funded and accessible themselves.
- **Purpose must drive triage and strategy.** Wing urged the group to think carefully about what's actually at risk and why it matters. For continuous observational data—ocean conditions, weather systems—gaps in collection destroy the dataset's utility. Time series cannot simply be resumed after interruption. The field needs to conduct model sensitivity analyses to understand which data inputs are most critical.

Environmental Justice and the Data Center Boom

Cecilia Marrinan of the Kapor Foundation addressed the topic of the physical infrastructure required for data, with a deep dive into a case study on the environmental impacts of data centers. She brought attention to the emerging crisis of proliferating data centers in already-vulnerable California communities, revealing how the physical infrastructure of the digital economy reproduces environmental racism.

Marrinan found that the median pollution burden score of data centers is in the top 20% of most environmentally impacted locations in California. Nearly one-third of data centers are located in the top 10% of areas most polluted by diesel particulate matter. Yet the industry's environmental, social, and governance (ESG) frameworks treat location as a neutral factor, a form of greenwashing that ignores cumulative impacts on fenceline communities.

The same communities fighting for access to environmental data about the harms they face are now grappling with the physical infrastructure of data storage itself becoming a new source of harm. Marrinan offered recommendations that could improve outcomes for data infrastructure resilience and environmental impact:

- **Update industrial zoning** classifications so that they learn from historical patterns of environmental injustice,
- **Support community-led policy interventions**, that address community concerns about data center siting
- **Mandate reporting, and increase transparency** in terms of energy use and water demands

The Landscape of Threats: A Collective Mapping

Participants broke into small groups to surface additional threats and cluster emerging themes. What resulted was a map of interconnected challenges spanning technical, social, institutional, and political dimensions.

- **Coordination and strategy gaps were the most frequently cited challenges.**
The field is working in long-standing silos with insufficient knowledge of who is doing what, making it difficult to avoid duplication, identify gaps, or move with collective power. The scale and speed of attacks makes prioritization difficult, and there's no clear authority in civil society to set strategic direction. Without better coordination, the field risks remaining trapped in reactive, band-aid responses that mirror the status quo rather than building long-term strategic solutions.
- **Loss of people and capacity is foundational to nearly every other challenge.**
The scale of Reductions In Force, hiring freezes, and departures, as well as the loss of institutional knowledge and expertise from the public sector, are profound. Data stewardship, the human work of curation, documentation, and maintenance, is systematically devalued even as its importance becomes clearer. Those doing data rescue and preservation work face burnout, and the field struggles to hire and retain data professionals who command far higher salaries in Big Tech.
- **Data quality and continuity challenges compound as federal capacity erodes.**
Discontinued data collection programs create gaps that may never be filled. Data that remains online receives less funding and staff support, leading to quality degradation and stagnation. Provenance, metadata, and documentation, already weak in many systems, become harder to maintain. When data stops being updated, users may not realize they're working with outdated information, creating new risks.
- **Discovery and access challenges mean that even preserved data may be difficult to find and use.**
All data systems, be they distributed or centralized, require discoverability mechanisms, and there is no standardized way to indicate data losses (e.g., through error codes). The current data landscape is incomplete and constantly shifting, and the tools and platforms that made data usable are being removed as agencies align their digital assets with administration priorities.
- **Polarization has decreased trust in science, while simulationally politicized agency leadership has eroded trust in government.**
Public distrust in government devalues data and science conducted both within and beyond government, making it harder to collect new data through surveys, voluntary reporting, or new collaborations. Even when data are collected and available, communities may not use or trust them without better documentation, context, and connection to action. The "chilling environment" makes it unsafe for some to speak up about what's being lost. Building trust in non-federal data sources while maintaining quality standards presents its own challenges.
- **Generative AI introduces both new threats and uncertain promises.**
The data center boom creates environmental burdens in vulnerable communities while consuming massive amounts of energy. AI models are often trained with older and sometimes outdated data. This can embed bad assumptions and fossil fuel dominance into algorithmic systems. Growing reliance on AI raises risks around transparency, quality, and equity. Yet AI represents potential capacity if data centers and compute resources can be deployed ethically, sustainably, and in service of public goods, rather than purely commercial interests.

- **Navigating private-public partnerships creates existential tensions**
Growing dependence on Big Tech and the private sector creates fragility, but entirely rejecting collaboration with private entities ignores potential resources. Though problematic privatization occurs, genuinely beneficial partnerships are also possible, especially when private sector actors are incentivized to collect, manage, and share data sustainably. There's a need to finance "non-sexy public goods" that maintain our current data infrastructure alongside the "new shiny things" that allow us to push forward in new directions.
- **Legal and policy gaps leave the field vulnerable to dramatic shifts based on who is in power and political whims**
Existing laws and policies provide insufficient protection against data suppression, removal, and loss of public access. There's limited clarity on what legal mechanisms can contest data loss. The field needs joint policy alignment and advocacy, but lacks coordination to pursue it effectively.
- **Communities already bearing disproportionate environmental burdens face compounding harms from data infrastructure collapse.**
Continued burdens in underserved communities, exacerbated health inequities, and community disempowerment are not side effects; they are central consequences of infrastructure collapse. Systematic targeting and dismantling of data and tools that serve communities make it harder for those most impacted by environmental injustice to demonstrate harm, compounded by government actors targeting environmental justice organizations doing this work.

A System Under Compound Stress

The group mapping revealed a system under compound stress where challenges build on one another. The loss of federal personnel reduces data quality and collection, which erodes public trust, which makes data collection harder, which increases reliance on private sector alternatives, which concentrates power and creates new vulnerabilities. Communities facing environmental injustice lose access to the data needed to document harms at the same moment that new harms (like data centers) are sited in their neighborhoods. Five cross-cutting themes emerged from the small group discussions:

1. **Overwhelming scale and velocity:** The volume of changes happening daily creates "data vertigo" and risks burnout across the field.
2. **Urgent need for prioritization:** Given the scope of threats, the field must choose its battles strategically, rather than trying to address everything at once.
3. **Justice as a prioritization lens:** Social justice implications may provide the framework for setting priorities about what to preserve and build.
4. **Dual focus required:** The field must simultaneously preserve existing datasets and shape future data collection systems.
5. **Communication and public mobilization:** Better storytelling and public engagement are essential to build the constituency needed to defend and sustain data infrastructure.

What's Still Standing? Bright Spots and Baselines

Against the backdrop of loss and threat, we shifted focus to resilience and work already underway to preserve, rebuild, and reimagine environmental data infrastructure. Lightning presentations showcased the diversity of approaches emerging across the field. While these represented only a subset of efforts, they illustrated broader patterns of work happening across multiple fronts. Several themes emerged across these presentations:

- **Mobilizing quickly and at-scale.** The community has demonstrated remarkable capacity for rapid response—standing up new organizations, coordinating volunteers, and archiving massive amounts of data within months.
- **Moving from reactive to strategic.** While preservation remains urgent, groups are increasingly focused on building durable infrastructure, establishing governance frameworks, and creating coordination mechanisms that outlast the current crisis.
- **Coordinating and reducing fragmentation.** Nearly every presenter identified coordination gaps as both a challenge and a priority, with multiple organizations building infrastructure specifically to connect disparate efforts.
- **Recognizing the foundation of human capacity.** Data infrastructure is inseparable from the people who build and maintain it. Given the extensive capacity cuts, networks of fellowships have emerged like the Aspen Global Climate Initiative's Strengthening Human Infrastructure Project (SHIP), New America and Environmental Policy Innovation's Digital Service for the Planet and NY Climate Exchange's talent preservation efforts.
- **Diversifying funding and governance models.** Organizations are experimenting with different structures—coalitions, collaboratives, independent nonprofits, academic partnerships—and seeking models to sustain work that has historically been dependent on federal funding.
- **Designing for justice and accessibility.** Multiple efforts explicitly center community needs, environmental justice, and equitable access, moving beyond preservation toward building infrastructure that serves those most impacted.
- **Bridging research and action.** Several initiatives focus on connecting data to decision-making, whether through emissions portals for communities, tools for policy advocacy, or frameworks that bridge from research to implementation.

These bright spots reveal an emergent ecosystem adapting rapidly to crisis while planting seeds for long-term transformation. The field has moved from asking "how do we preserve what's being lost?" to "how do we build something more resilient, just, and effective?" The question for the remainder of our time became: *how do we move from parallel efforts to collective action?*

If We Could Build It – Naming Our North Star

The third session of the workshop shifted from assessment to aspiration. Having mapped threats and identified existing capacity, we engaged in collective visioning: What would a truly resilient, open, community-centered, environmental data infrastructure look like? What do we want to focus on together? The conversation produced both ambitious end-state visions and concrete principles for working toward them. Participants articulated goals across three dimensions: the world they want to create, pathways toward those goals, and how they want to work together.

The World We Want: Structural Visions

Federated and collaborative—not centralized— data systems. The strongest consensus emerged around moving away from single-point-of-failure architectures toward federated models that balance power between sectors. As one participant framed it: "No single point of failure. Federated, rather than centralized models." This principle applies both technically (i.e., distributed data collection and storage and access following the LOCKSS tenet—"Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe") and institutionally (i.e., collaborative infrastructures that connect organizations rather than concentrate power).

Federal government as an irreplaceable partner. Even while building distributed capacity, participants emphasized that nothing can replace the federal government's role in producing essential environmental datasets. Stop-gap measures created during this crisis might inadvertently bolster arguments for privatizing federal data responsibilities. As one participant put it, the field must demonstrate what's possible through innovation while simultaneously defending the necessity of federal investment in public data infrastructure.

A balance of power across stakeholders. Rather than government *or* industry *or* community data, our vision embraces "a balance of power between different stakeholders: private, philanthropic, government, community, in shaping datasets and their governance." Resilience requires multiple sectors while ensuring no single sector dominates.

Being prepared for future transitions. Multiple participants called for "Project 2029"—an environmental and data policy playbook for the next administration change that also informs state and local efforts. The field needs policies and protections in place to prevent recurrence of the current situation, regardless of which party holds power. State and local governments will need models and supportive policies as they continue to steward environmental data and contend with waning federal support.

Pathways: How to Get There

Community understanding and buy-in. For data infrastructure to be truly resilient, communities must understand, value, and buy into data creation, stewardship, and use. This requires moving beyond technical excellence to emotional connection. As one participant argued: "Rebrand 'data'—need superhero storytelling for data that taps into emotions...The word 'data' can provoke boredom or distrust for most people. Measurement; Evidence; Proof." Building constituencies who defend data because they use it is itself a resilience strategy.

Sustainable business models for stewardship. Participants acknowledged struggling to identify sustainable funding for public good data infrastructure without government support. Data stewardship needs "a sustainable business model" and "some level of core support if not the feds." This includes making it easier for data stewards to identify third-party use-cases for their data, helping them design structures, standards, and access with others in mind.

Permission to let things go. In a memorable phrase, participants called for "joyful funerals... for things that aren't adding significant value." The field should celebrate the work datasets did, and let them go when they're no longer needed (or when they are actively harmful). This requires developing evaluation models to distinguish such datasets from data that remains essential.

Less bureaucratic siloing, or, strategic redundancy. Participants wanted to move from "each agency has its own model for very similar things" toward "best-of-USG/US data" when aims are similar enough, reducing needless redundancy. At the same time, strategic redundancy through distributed storage and federated access provides resilience against loss.

How We Want to Work: Process and Principles

Build in, don't buy in.

As one participant noted: "If you participate in the process, you don't have to [be convinced]." Inclusivity from the start creates ownership and reduces the burden of later persuasion. This applies to both technical design (programmer- and builder-friendly systems where minor technical barriers don't accumulate) and governance (ensuring communities are leading forces in data collection, not just consulted afterward).

Play to strengths and respect lanes.

Rather than everyone doing everything, the vision emphasizes "play to org's strengths—respect yourselves and their lanes. Be here, contribute while you can, and do the work you are best suited to do." Inherent in this is a desire to be "mutually supportive of projects across this space." This requires good coordination to know who's doing what without exhausting everyone through duplication.

Honor FAIR and CARE principles.

Technical interoperability through FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) must be coupled with CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles for Indigenous data governance. Data sovereignty must be appropriate and clear, with licensing structures that give communities operational control over how data about them is collected, used, and interpreted.

Create non-extractive, community-led processes.

Data must not be extractive or harmful for represented communities; communities should be the leading force in data collection. This includes identifying and examining the field's own biases to avoid colonial approaches in data creation, governance, and use. Beyond consultation, communities need enforceable control over how data about them is collected, used, and interpreted.

Design for sharing.

Data should be designed to be shared from the start (even if it will have access and use limits), with interoperability built in from the get-go and support for data stewards to maintain that data. This reduces barriers to cross-system analysis while respecting necessary protections.

Ensure quality and legal defensibility.

Data must have the quality and capability to support decisions that may be challenged in court, or, conversely, to bring legal challenges. This is not just a technical standard but a justice requirement—communities need data robust enough to withstand well-resourced opposition.

The vision emerging from this session is ambitious: infrastructure that is simultaneously more resilient, more just, more usable, and more sustainable than what existed before. It requires technical innovation, governance reform, cultural change, sustainable funding, and political protection. The question for the final sessions became: where do we start?

From Vision to Action: Six Coordinated Sprints

Day 2 focused on translating vision and coordination needs into concrete, time-bound sprints that correspond to identified priority areas for exploration and action. Participants pitched ideas and organized into six working groups. The sprints reflect the diversity of the identified gaps, spanning human capacity, funding models, cross-organizational coordination, community data governance, legal strategy, and technical interoperability.

- **Sprint 1: Building Capacity of Data Stewards**
Challenge: Volunteer burnout threatens the sustainability of data rescue and stewardship efforts across organizations.
Why it matters: For the field to be equitable and sustainable, organizations need strategies that value volunteers' time and create pathways for meaningful contribution without burnout.
Approach: Pilot and document key strategies to increase knowledge around data stewardship and build volunteer capacity, creating shareable best practices for improving retention and satisfaction.
- **Sprint 2: New Funding Models and Sustainable Infrastructure**
Challenge: Loss of government funding puts national datasets at risk, while repositories' bespoke infrastructures make coordination difficult and leave them vulnerable to being "picked off" by industry one-by-one.
Why it matters: The field needs sustainable funding models that don't depend solely on government or purely extract value through privatization.
Approach: Federate organizations to generate diversified, sustainable funding by exploring how commercial uses of publicly-funded data could generate revenue that flows back to research and infrastructure.
- **Sprint 3: Cross-Organizational Coordination**
Challenge: Fragmented, uncoordinated efforts across the field with no clear mechanism to identify actors, set priorities, or enable strategic collaboration risks undermining impact and creating redundancies.
Why it matters: "Federation can bring ideas up from the bottom for funders" rather than funders guessing field needs; coordination can identify flagship datasets, connect them to displaced federal stewards, and socialize criteria for what's essential to defend.
Approach: Develop a coordinating body through a phased process starting with landscape analysis, bring groups together for briefing and participation, and create a leadership taskforce. Pilot coordination around greenhouse gas emissions data as an immediate test case.
- **Sprint 4: Community-Generated and -Validated Data**
Challenge: Community data is undervalued and underutilized; current systems make community control of data use and interpretation the exception rather than the norm, shutting community needs and perspectives out of research.
Why it matters: Communities need enforceable control over data about them, and data must be robust enough to support legal challenges or enable communities to bring challenges against environmental harms.
Approach: Conduct a discovery process to examine how to pair qualitative and quantitative data, define validation standards respecting multiple forms of evidence, identify projects doing this well, and compile examples with transparent tradeoffs into an implementation toolkit.
- **Sprint 5: Legal, Policy, and Legislative Strategies**
Challenge: Existing legal protections are under-utilized in essential data preservation efforts, and non-experts need ways to assess environmental data quality for litigation purposes.

Why it matters: Post-Chevron, courts have expanded power to evaluate agency science, and establishing what constitutes reliable science becomes critical for defending public data and enabling communities to use data in legal challenges.

Approach: Analyze legal protections and litigation issues to scope rapid response strategy. Simultaneously, work with data stewards to codify QA/QC procedures and develop validation systems that satisfy both scientific standards and legal requirements.

- **Sprint 6: Data Interoperability and Communities of Practice**

Challenge: Data quality is likely dropping as capacity degrades but is difficult to assess; inconsistent metadata and standards across domains make it harder to connect and use data effectively.

Why it matters: Data becomes less useful over time without maintenance, documentation, and knowledge about quality and appropriate uses; interoperability is essential for integrated analysis across climate, health, and demographic data to show cumulative impacts.

Approach: Build communities of practice around cross-domain interoperability standards (learning from models like CMIP, AgMIP, and genomics frameworks) and dataset-specific quality assessment. Create spaces to share knowledge about data quality issues and appropriate use cases.

The sprints represent a portfolio approach: experimenting with multiple interventions simultaneously, learning from each, and looking for opportunities to amplify or connect them.

Conclusion: From Crisis Response to Systems Building

The Future of Open Environmental Data Infrastructure workshop offered an opportunity to move toward collective visioning of more resilient, just, and sustainable infrastructure. The two days produced both sobering assessment and energizing action: a comprehensive mapping of threats and losses, identification of significant existing capacity and bright spots, articulation of shared values and aspirational goals, and commitment to six concrete action sprints.

One year into an administration that has systematically dismantled environmental data infrastructure, the field gathered not just to mourn what's been lost but to build what comes next. The question is no longer whether the old system can be restored but whether something better can emerge from this crisis. The Oakland convening gave a resounding "yes!" Our conversations revealed our field's commitment and eagerness to build data infrastructure that is more resilient, just, sustainable, and ultimately of service to ever-urgent environmental and climate problems.

Addendum: September 2025 Workshop Agenda

Infrastructure Workshop

Why This, Why Now

This is a defining moment for open environmental data. Over the past year, the U.S. has seen foundational environmental datasets removed or defunded, long-standing tools dismantled, and public access to information about climate, health, and justice quietly rolled back. Decades of scientific expertise and institutional knowledge have been lost due to cuts in federal staffing and funding for research partners. The infrastructure supporting environmental data—people, technology, governance—is being systematically dismantled.

But there are also bright spots: grassroots archiving networks, new collaborations, community-led innovations, and private funders investing in science. We are seeing the seeds of a new environmental data infrastructure, one that could address some of the failures of the past, while also taking advantage of innovations in data science and architecture, such as artificial intelligence.

We believe this moment requires more than reaction; it calls for collective visioning. What kind of infrastructure do we want to build next? What scaffolding—technical, institutional, legal, and relational—will we need to sustain it?

This workshop is the first step to co-create that future.

About the Workshop

Open Environmental Data Project (OEDP) in partnership with the Public Environmental Data Partners coalition (PEDP), the Center for Open Data Enterprise (CODE) and the Kapor Center are bringing together a cross-sector network of researchers, community leaders, data stewards, technologists, civil society advocates, government stakeholders, and funders to chart a course toward resilient, just, and open environmental data systems.

This work builds on:

- Urgent field-wide efforts to defend environmental data access, including PEDP's rapid-response archiving;
- Long-term conversations about science and data infrastructure, including events hosted by Aspen Global Climate Initiative (AGCI), the Federation of American Scientists (FAS), Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP), The National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) and others;
- And the need to move from short-term triage toward long-term systems change.

While this workshop is focused on the future of environmental data infrastructure in the United States, we recognize that many of the challenges and opportunities, especially around AI, resilience, and stewardship, are global in nature. Integration with international networks may be part of the solution, and we hope to include select international participants who can offer insight and alignment from global efforts.

Core Questions

As we begin this process, we are inviting our coalition and partners to reflect on a few key questions that will guide our collective design:

1. What is left that we can build from?

In a moment of loss, what are the bright spots? Where is meaningful work already happening that we can learn from or scale?

2. What does our ideal future look like?

If we could start fresh and build an environmental data infrastructure that is ethical, durable, and community-centered, what would it look like? What values would guide it? Who would be involved?

3. How do we begin scaffolding that future, even if not everyone is here yet? What can we do now to set the conditions for that future? How do we document, prototype, and share in ways that invite others to join us later?

OEDP is providing a pre-reading of suggested [Design Principles for our Future Environmental Data Infrastructure](#), which includes a list of additional readings for those who want to go deeper. We welcome further iteration and discussion of these principles throughout the event.

DAY 1: Co-Creating the Future of Open Environmental Data

9:00 - 10:15 a.m. | Opening Circle: Setting the Frame

Grounding the convening's purpose, goals, and shared values.

10:15 - 11:15 a.m. | Session 1: What Are We Up Against?

Presentations on the current state in 2025 followed by workshoping a list of shared challenges.

Presentations by:

- EDGI Report on [Climate of Suppression](#) - Gretchen Gherke
- CODE Report on [America's Data Future](#) - Joel Gurin
- Intertidal Agency (Data Collection) - Kate Wing
- Kapor Foundation (Data Centers) - Cecilia Marrinan

11:30 a.m. - 12:30 p.m. | Session 2: What's Still Standing?

Spotlight on bright spots and existing assets in the field.

Presentations by:

- Public Environmental Data Partners (PEDP) - Jessie Mahr (EPIC)
- Impact Project - Abby André
- Data Rescue Project - Lynda Kellam
- Data Foundation - Sonia Wang
- AGU - Shelley Stall
- NY Climate Exchange - Andel Koester
- Strengthening Human Infrastructure Project (SHIP) Coalition - Julie Vano (ACGI)
- [EssentialData.US](#) - Denice Ross

1:30 - 2:40 p.m. | Session 3: If We Could Build It

Collaborative visioning: What would a resilient, community-centered, open data infrastructure look like? What's the future we all want to build?

3:00 - 4:05 p.m. | Session 4: What Will It Take?

What capacities—technical, institutional, legal, human—do we need to invest in?
Identifying what's underway, what's missing, and what each of us can contribute.

4:05 - 5:00 p.m. | Closing Reflections

Themes and threads emerging from the day; what needs deeper exploration and next steps.

Day 2: Building Forward

9:00 - 9:15 a.m. | Welcome Back & Framing the Day

9:15 - 11:00 a.m. | Working Session: Where Do We Go From Here? What tools, frameworks, or collaborations should we prioritize?

Small group break-outs to decide on some concrete things we may want to try together.

11:15 a.m.–12:30 p.m. | Full Group Synthesis

Group share-out of key ideas and priorities.

Identifying interest areas for future working groups or action tracks.

12:30 - 1:00 p.m. | Closing Circle

Reflections, appreciations, and next steps. Setting momentum for what's ahead.